

PSSOH (Applications of Free Software and Open Hardware) Conference Report

PLACE & DATE of the Conference: main building of the University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering (ETF), [Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade](#) (ground floor, room 61), October 13, 2018.

The first PSSOH conference consisted of 17 lectures related to applications of free software and open hardware and to women and other minority groups representation in the electrical engineering and computer science. The majority of PSSOH lecturers were from the University of Belgrade (School of Electrical Engineering and Faculty of Philosophy), but also from the office of the Commissioner for Protection of Equality in Serbia, Wikimedia Serbia, University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Technical Sciences in Serbia, University of Kragujevac – Faculty of Engineering in Serbia, University of Ljubljana - Faculty of Electrical Engineering in Slovenia, Medtronic Zagreb in Croatia, University of Belgrade Computer Center, Institute of Technical Sciences of SASA, Research Centre for Cheminformatics, Institute of Psychology, and Laboratory for Research of Individual Differences at the University of Belgrade.

Logistics for the conference were provided by the organizer, University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering, with strong support of the Dean Prof. Dr. Milo Tomašević. Ten volunteers participated in the conference organization that was supported by two public donors Academic Mind from Belgrade, Serbia, and Nervtech from Ljubljana, Slovenia. Many partners supported our event: University of Novi Sad – Faculty of Technical Sciences, Laboratory for Information Technologies from the University of Ljubljana – Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Teodesk company from Belgrade, KELM laboratory from Novi Sad, BeFEM Feminist Cultural Center from Belgrade, Serbia, Data Science Serbia, Women’s studies center from Belgrade, Serbia, R-Ladies Belgrade, LiBRE magazine, and the last but not the least Free Software Foundation Europe. We are also supported by our partner conferences “Let it be MIT” from the University of Novi Sad Serbia and SatRday Conference in Belgrade Serbia.

Proceedings of the first PSSOH Conference are available online at [PSSOH site](#) together with PSSOH Agenda at the Zenodo repository (DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.1443501](#)).

PSSOH consisted of four sessions: an Introductory Session with special invited lecture from Dipl. Eng. Dragan Satarić from Wikimedia Serbia on the free software and open culture in Serbia, two sessions with application of free software and open hardware in various fields and areas, and one session that covers issues of representation of women and minority groups in electrical engineering and computer science.

Session I consisted of 5 lectures on the following topics: (1) free instruction set architecture (RISC-V), (2) historical perspective and future developments of R programming language on its 25th anniversary, (3) lecture on reverse engineering for dual licensing violation detection, (4) the need for open science and advantages it offers, and (5) on institutional repositories (Dspace). In Session II, 5 more lectures were presented, including topics on application of open hardware in biomedical measurements and for assessment of cognitive workload of drivers, with lecture on GNU/Linux evolution through history. Last two lectures were related to education at the University of Belgrade (open educational resources and teaching Python to freshmen). The fourth session was devoted to women in computer science and electrical engineering. We had a chance to hear about life and work of Ada Byron, about gender disparities in computer science in Serbia and all around the world, and a pleasure to be inspired by the experiences of our colleague Ela Vidović in the area of clinical engineering.

Two specific parts of PSSOH Conference that attracted lots of attention were:

- Premiere of a documentary movie “Film o srpskim naučnicama” (“Movie About Serbian Female Scientists”) authored by Boris Simić, Todor Milivojević, and Sava Nikolić, students from “[Nikola](#)

[Tesla](#)” high school in cooperation with [Center for the Promotion of Science](#), [Hypatia](#) EU project, Belgrade, Serbia

- Exhibition during the coffee break, never presented before: “The beginnings of Data Science in Yugoslavia”. The exhibition included plots of telegraphic traffic before, during, and after assassination of [Alexander I of Yugoslavia](#) in Marseilles, France on October 9, 1934, about 84 years ago. The diagrams were hidden behind an old locker in an ETF office for more than 80 years were exposed to the daylight and gaze at our audience for the very first time! We’ve opened the door to set these data free! Organizers of the event were [ETF](#) and [Postal Museum](#).

DATE of the Post-conference Events: October 20, 2018.

Overall, 41 participants (more than 50% of the participants were university students) attended two post-conference lectures (“Copyright and Free Licenses for Researchers” and “Introduction to Python with Applications in Electrical Measurements”), and a post-conference course (“R for Data Science”). Around 60 people attended PSSOH conference, about 30% of them being university students.

All relevant information can be found at PSSOH site and GitHub and Twitter pages (<http://pssoh.etf.bg.ac.rs/>).

Selected photos of PSSOH Conference

